

Food Recommendation System Using Machine Learning

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Abstract— This research paper explores the use of cosine similarity in personalized food recommendation systems. With the increasing number of food items available to consumers, it has become essential to provide relevant and personalized food recommendations to improve customer satisfaction. This study aims to contribute to the field of food technology by introducing a more accurate and efficient method for recommending food items to users. By utilizing unsupervised machine learning techniques, this study seeks to provide insights into the factors that influence food preferences and how cosine similarity can help improve recommendation accuracy. The findings of this research can assist food industry stakeholders in making better decisions related to menu planning, food marketing, and personalized food delivery, ultimately leading to improved customer experiences and increased revenue.

Keywords— Machine learning, Cosine Similarity, Food Recommendation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The food industry has become increasingly day to day, with consumers demanding personalized and relevant food recommendations. Traditional methods of recommending food items to users may not always be accurate, as they do not consider various factors that can influence food preferences. Machine learning algorithms have emerged as a solution to this problem, as they can analyze large amounts of data and identify patterns those traditional methods. This research paper explores the use of unsupervised machine learning techniques, specifically cosine similarity, in personalized food recommendation systems and food will recommend based on the availability. By providing more accurate and efficient methods for recommending food items to consumers, machine learning can help food industry stakeholders make data-driven decisions related to menu planning, food marketing, and personalized food delivery. The ultimate goal of this research is to enhance customer satisfaction and increase revenue for food industry stakeholders.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Users' recommendations for food products have increase recently. Many strategies have been proposed, including collaborative filtering, content-based filtering, and hybrid models. While content-based filtering uses items, collaborative filtering uses past user behavior to

items, collaborative filtering uses past user behavior to suggest specific foods.

MEHRDAD ROSTAMI, MOURAD OUSSALAH (Senior Member, IEEE), AND VAHID FARRAHI [1]. This paper proposes a new hybrid food recommender-system that aims to address the limitations of previous systems by considering food ingredients, time factor, cold start users, cold start food items, and community aspects. The proposed method involves two phases: food content-based recommendation and user-based recommendation, where graph clustering is used in the first phase, and a deep-learning-based approach is used in the second phase to cluster both users and food items.

Weeing Min, Member, IEEE, Shuping Jiang, Member, IEEE, Ramesh Jain.[2] The article proposes a unified framework for food recommendation to address the growing problem of unhealthy eating patterns and the resulting increase in diseases such as diabetes, heart disease, and cancer. The authors identify various issues affecting food recommendation, such as incorporating context and domain knowledge, building personal models, and analyzing unique food characteristics.

Pratiksha Ashok. Naik Information Technology SDMCET Dharwad[3].The paper proposes an intelligent food recommendation system that utilizes machine learning techniques to provide personalized recommendations based on the user's preferences and dislikes. The system is trained using the recommendations received from customers who have already used the product, which helps to ensure that the recommendations are relevant and accurate. Overall, this paper is a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners in the field of recommender systems.

Atharva Palekar, Juhi Vic hare, Jay Tarak, Prof. Prachi Kharghar (2021) in Food recommendation system [4]. The paper discusses the increasing attention given to food recommender systems in promoting healthy living. Most existing studies in this area focus on providing personalized recommendations based on the user's preferences or health issues. The paper presents an overview of recommendation methods in the healthy food domain and reviews the current food recommender systems.

RACIEL YERA, LUIS MARTINEZ [5]. The paper presents a novel approach to personalized food recommendation by incorporating both nutritional and preference-aware information in a general framework for daily meal plan recommendations. The proposed system includes a pre-filtering stage to exclude foods that are not suitable for the user's characteristics and an optimization-based stage to generate a daily meal plan that satisfies the user's nutritional requirements and preferences.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for building a content-based food recommendation system typically involves the following steps:

- A. Data Collection
- B. Data Pre-processing
- C. Model Building
- D. Analyzing
- E. Result

A. Data Collection:

- Collecting data about food items, such as their names, descriptions.
- This data can be obtained from various sources such as restaurant menus, food blogs, recipe websites, and food delivery apps.

B. Data Pre-processing:

- Cleaning and formatting the data to ensure consistency and accuracy.
- Removing stop words and irrelevant words from the food descriptions.

C. Model Building:

- Using a machine learning algorithm such as TF-IDF or word embeddings to generate a feature vector for each food item based on its description.
- Calculating pairwise similarity scores between the feature vectors of all
- food items using a similarity measure such as cosine similarity.
- Using the similarity scores to identify the most similar food items to a given query food item.

D. Analyzing:

- Evaluating the performance of the model using metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score.

Machine Learning: To train a model that can comprehend the relationship between various food items based on their features such as description, etc., machine learning is used in the content-based filtering approach for food recommendation. The model learns to spot patterns in the data that can aid in making recommendations after being trained on a dataset of food items and their attributes. By allowing the model to learn from data and make precise recommendations based on the characteristics of various food items, machine learning overall plays a key role in the content-based filtering approach for food recommendation.

IV. ALGORITHM

- Load the food data from a CSV file using pandas' library.
- Food can recommend based on availability of food.
- When a user inputs a food name, the code checks that recommended foods are available in it. If not found, it returns None.
- If found, the code computes the cosine similarity between the input food and all other foods using cosine similarity function from the sklearn.metrics.Pairwise module.
- The code then returns a list of recommended foods based on their similarity scores, sorted in descending order.
- The number of recommendations is determined by the user input for 'num_recommendations'.
- Finally, the recommended food names are returned to the user interface as a list.

1) TF-IDF algorithm

TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) algorithm - It is used for text preprocessing and vectorization of the food descriptions. It assigns a numerical value to each word in the corpus based on its frequency in a given document and its rarity in the entire corpus.

2) Cosine Similarity algorithm

Cosine Similarity algorithm - It is used to calculate the similarity between the user-input food and all other foods in the dataset. Cosine similarity measures the cosine of the angle between two vectors in a high-dimensional space. It is a commonly used algorithm for text similarity and recommendation systems.

- 1) Import the libraries required and then import and print the dataset.

```
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer
from sklearn.metrics.pairwise import cosine_similarity
from flask import Flask, request, render_template
```

2) Loading Food Data from CSV File

```
food_data = pd.read_csv(r'food.csv')
```

3) Preprocessing Food Data

```
tfidf = TfidfVectorizer(stop_words='english')  
food_data['description'] = food_data['description'].fillna('')  
food_matrix = tfidf.fit_transform(food_data['description'])
```

4) Creating Flask App

```
app = Flask(__name__)
```

5) Setting Up Homepage Route

```
@app.route('/')  
def home():  
    return render_template('hhh.html')
```

6) Setting Up Food Recommendation Route

```
app = Flask(__name__)  
  
@app.route('/')  
def home():  
    return render_template('hhh.html')  
  
@app.route('/recommend', methods=['POST'])  
@app.route('/recommend', methods=['POST'])  
def recommend_food():  
    food_name = request.form.get('food_name').lower() # convert input to lowercase  
    num_recommendations = int(request.form.get('num_recommendations'))  
    if food_name not in map(str.lower, food_data['food_name'].values):  
        return None # return None if food not found  
    else:  
        food_index = food_data[food_data['food_name'].str.lower() == food_name].index[0]  
        similarity_scores = cosine_similarity(food_matrix[food_index], food_matrix).flatten()  
        related_food_indices = similarity_scores.argsort()[::-1][1:num_recommendations + 1]  
        related_food = food_data.iloc[related_food_indices]['food_name']  
        return list(related_food.values)
```

V. RESULT

Food Recommendation System

Food Item:

Bread

Number of
Recommendations:

2

Get Recommendations

Nutella
Jam

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, food recommendation systems have become an important application in machine learning. By using content-based filtering, we can find out the relationship between different food based on the description and recommend similar food items with their availability.

REFERENCES

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